

LIBERTY UNIVERSITY SCHOOL OF DIVINITY

An Analysis of Ephesians 4:7-16 Including Controversies, its Use, and its Understanding over
the Course of the Christian Era

Submitted to Dr. Jerry Pounds,
in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the completion of

RTCH 500 – D09 LUO
Research, Writing, and Ministry Preparation

by

John Daniels, M.Ed.

May 5, 2019

Introduction

The city of Ephesus was a Greek Colony in Anatolia. It was defined through history by its proximity to three hills that are in modern times known as Bulbul Dagh, Panayir Dagh, and Ayasokuk. In the time of Paul and his letters, the city was in the valley between hills Panayir Dagh and Bulbul Dagh.¹

The Letter to the Ephesians might be a misnomer. The work may have been written to the Laodiceans or even to several churches throughout the Roman Province of Asia. The earliest known copies of the letter such as the Chester Beatty Papyri from AD 200 do not give the Church of Ephesus as the recipient. However, it is also possible that Ephesus was taken out of the manuscript in later copies to make the message more general in nature.²

One of the most well-known passages from Ephesians comprises chapter four verses seven through sixteen. The passage lists the many positions of leadership associated with gifts from the Holy Spirit to guide and grow the body of Christ. **The purpose of this paper is to show that Paul is listing leadership positions that correspond to spiritual gifts. While some of these positions no longer exist in the Earthly Church, the rest form a unity to grow the Body of Christ.**

¹David Noel Freedman, "Ephesus," *The Anchor Yale Bible Dictionary* (New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 2009), pp. 542. Logos.

² Francis Foulkes, *Ephesians: An Introduction and Commentary* (Downers Grove, IL: Inter-Varsity Press, 2008), 22-25. Logos.

Literary Genre

Ephesians falls under the literary genre of an epistle. Epistles were letters and should be read as such, despite the modern conventions of chapter-and-verse divisions in the Bible. It should be read through completely until the reader can determine the concerns and purposes of the author, the argument and the way it is developed, the connections of its verses with those found in other books of the Bible, and the way the verses in the letter interact with one another.³ In ancient times epistles were used to preserve the ideas of a teacher, defend doctrines, attract new adherents, or to convince followers to live according to the mandates of their philosophy. Examples of philosophies that were conveyed via epistles include Cynicism, Stoicism, Epicureanism, and Christianity.⁴

Context

The Letter to the Ephesians was written by the Apostle Paul. After the initial Twelve Apostles and Matthias (Acts 1:12), Paul was commissioned by Christ as the apostle to the Gentiles⁵ (Acts 9:4-16). Paul was born as Saul in the city of Tarsus. He was a Roman citizen which would aid him later in his interactions with government officials.

³ Walter C. Kaiser and Silva Moisés, *An Introduction to Biblical Hermeneutics: The Search for Meaning* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2007), 175. Wordsearch Bible.

⁴ Patrick Gray, *Opening Paul's Letters: A Reader's Guide to Genre and Interpretation* (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2012), 39. Logos.

⁵ After the rebellion of the people at the Tower of Babel, Yahweh disinherited them and split them up into nations via languages. He then created Israel via the miraculous birth of Isaac to be His people (Deuteronomy 32:8-9). Paul speaks of the grafting of the Gentiles back into the family of Yahweh as the mystery of Christ (Ephesians 3:4-6).

He received rabbinic training in Jerusalem from the Pharisee rabbi Gamaliel and at some point, also learned the profession of tentmaking.⁶ He was a fervent persecutor of the Christian sect of Judaism and at the time of his conversion was on his way to Damascus to detain and return Christians to Jerusalem (Acts 9:1-3).

The letter opens in a similar manner to Paul's other letters but does not include personal messages, greetings, or recollections beyond stating that Paul is in prison and the letter has been sent in care of Tychicus.⁷ In addition, it reads more as a sermon than a letter. These differences have led some modern scholars to dispute Pauline authorship, with some suggesting that it was written by Onesimus after Paul's death. However, it should be stated that no known writings from the early Church dispute its authorship (Foulkes p. 44-45).⁸ In defense of Pauline authorship when dealing specifically with Chapter 4:7-16, the list of church leadership roles is very similar to a list given in Paul's epistle to the Romans 12: 3-8.⁹

Meaning

Ephesians chapters 4-6 cover the responsibilities of Christians as part of the body of Christ.¹⁰ Verses 7-16 of chapter 4 deal with the giving of these gifts by the Holy Spirit and ties them to several leadership positions such as apostles and teachers (Ephesians 4:7-16). Verse seven starts off with the statement that the gifts are given by grace. No matter what spiritual gifts one has been given, they were not given on the grounds of merit and are not grounds for boasting.

⁶ Thomas D. Lea and David Alan Black, *The New Testament: Its Background and Message* (Nashville, TN: Broadman & Holman Publishers, 2007), 361. Wordsearch Bible.

⁷ Foulkes, 22.

⁸ Foulkes, 22.

⁹ Foulkes, 121.

¹⁰ Lea and Black, 462.

Verse eight contains an interesting alteration to a Psalm which states: “You ascended on high, leading a host of captives in your train and receiving gifts among men, even among the rebellious, that the Lord God may dwell there” (Psalm 68:18). In the broader context Yahweh returns to His throne after a great victory. In verses fifteen and sixteen the mountain of Bashan is stated to be jealous of Mount Zion. In the ancient Near east Cosmology the mountain of Bashan, or Mount Hermon, was a gateway to the realm of the dead.¹¹ So, Yahweh is returning victorious from a victory involving the realm of the dead with captives and receiving gifts from men.

When Paul quotes Psalm 68:18, he changes it to the following: “When he ascended on high, he led a host of captives, and he gave gifts to men.” (Ephesians 4:8). Instead of receiving gifts from mankind after conquering the realm of the dead, Christ is instead giving gifts out to His people.¹²

One puzzling part of the verse involves the procession of captives. Two interpretations of the identity of these captives are that they were either the forces of evil and death or that they are the captives of sin and death that have been freed by Christ.¹³ It doesn’t seem likely that the first choice is the case as Paul makes it clear later on in Ephesians that the Devil and the forces of evil are not yet captives and are still very real dangers to Christians (Ephesians 6:12).

¹¹ Michael S. Heiser, *Unseen Realm* (Lexham Press, 2015), 201. Kindle.

¹² There is precedence for the Holy Spirit leading Apostles to use Old Testament verses in new ways. For instance, in the Book of Acts, Peter combines portions of Psalm 69:25 and 109:8 to justify appointing a new apostle after the death of Judas (Acts 1:20-21).

¹³ Philip Wesley Comfort and Peter H. Davids, *Cornerstone Biblical Commentary: Ephesians, Philippians, Colossians, 1 & 2 Thessalonians, Philemon*, vol. 15 (Carol Stream, IL: Tyndale House Publishers, 2008), 81-82. Logos.

This leaves the captives being those freed from Sheol by the sacrifice of Christ. Just as Paul changed receiving gifts to giving gifts, the captives are changed from the enemy to the righteous dead. This would make sense as the Gospel of Matthew depicts the holy ones¹⁴ rising from their tombs after the resurrection of Christ (Matthew 27:52-53).

Verses nine and ten discuss the ascending and descending of Christ. In verse nine He descends to the lower regions of the earth and in verse ten he ascends far above all the heavens. In doing so He shows that nowhere in creation is absent of His spirit.¹⁵ There is some disagreement over the meaning and location of Christ's descent. Some scholars argue that the descent is the incarnation of Christ on Earth. Others argue that the descent is into the realm of the dead¹⁶ as described in 1 Peter. Still others state that the descent occurred as the giving of the Holy Spirit at Pentecost.¹⁷

Verse eleven moves into the leadership positions in the Church as determined by interactions with Christ and through gifts from the Holy Spirit. The positions are based on spiritual gifts and not church titles.¹⁸ The first position mentioned is the ultimate leadership position for Christians in the early Church. The word apostolos, Greek for apostle, is used in the Bible to denote a messenger, the primary twelve followers of Christ during His earthly ministry, and others including Matthias as Paul who obtained the title after the resurrection. Apostles were

¹⁴ Most translations use "saints" as the translation of the Greek hagios, but this obscures the meaning of several passages in the New Testament when compared to the more accurate translation of "holy one." See Michael S. Heiser, *Unseen Realm* (Lexham Press, 2015).

¹⁵ Foulkes, 123.

¹⁶ There is also disagreement as to what Christ did while in the realm of the dead. Many argue that He ministered to the dead to allow them to obtain salvation. However, 1 Peter states that the dead He proclaimed to the spirits that were imprisoned for their disobedience in the days of Noah (1 Peter 3:19-20). This and Jude 1:6 point to the sons of God in Genesis 6, especially in the context of 1 Enoch which was in circulation during the writing of the New Testament. See Michael S. Heiser, *Reversing Hermon: Enoch, the Watchers & the Forgotten Mission of Jesus Christ* (Crane, MO: Defender Publishing, 2017). Kindle.

¹⁷ Foulkes, 123.

¹⁸ Foulkes, 124. If it had been based on church titles, depending on the date Ephesians was written it might have included positions such as bishops and deacons.

foundational members of the Church that could act as witnesses to the life, teachings, and resurrection of Jesus Christ and perform miracles. One could only become an apostle through meeting the risen Christ and being appointed by Him.¹⁹ With the death of John the Revelator in AD 100, the Apostolic age ended, and no other apostles have been called since.²⁰

The next position mentioned in Ephesians 4 is the prophet. Prophets receive instructions from God and delivered the word of God to the people. Once the Word of God was codified in the New Testament, their purpose on Earth had ended.²¹ Evangelists are not discussed much in the New Testament. The Books of Acts and Timothy give us some clues (Acts 21:8) (2 Timothy 4:5) and the Greek euaggelistés means “a bringer of good news.” Therefore, the most likely function meant by Paul would be a missionary that planted churches in new areas.²²

The final two positions, pastors and teachers, are grouped together with the same article in the original Greek. Whereas the first set of positions dealt with the creation of churches, the final two deal with maintaining and growing these organizations. Pastor, a word meaning shepherd, denotes a Christian leader who guides a church like a shepherd guides a flock of sheep. While teachers are grouped with pastors and each pastor must in some degree be a teacher, they have specific spiritual gifts that distinguish them from the former.²³

¹⁹ Foulkes, 123. The exception to this rule might be Matthias. While he was chosen to replace Judas, he was not specifically appointed to the position by Christ. However, the use of drawing lots to determine the replacement is seen as requesting the advisement of the Lord. Proverbs states that the lot’s “every decision is from the Lord” (Proverbs 16:33).

²⁰ Walter A. Elwell, and Barry J. Beitzel, *Baker Encyclopedia of the Bible*. Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Book House, 1988. Logos.

²¹ Foulkes, 125-126. Much like apostles, prophets were specifically called by Yahweh. They were given their instructions before the Divine Council as related in the books of Isaiah and Jeremiah (Isaiah 6:1-12) (Jeremiah 23:18).

²² Foulkes, 126.

²³ Foulkes, 126.

Verse twelve follows this list of positions and states that these positions were created to better equip the holy ones for the ministry and building up the Body of Christ (Ephesians 4:12). There is some question regarding the grammar of the verse and whether the positions are meant to build up the ministry, or the entire body of Christ.²⁴ The last four verses of the chosen text deal with the unity of the body of Christ. Paul has listed the leadership positions for getting churches founded and sustained and now the whole picture comes together as a mature and focused universal church.²⁵ Ephesians 4:13 and 4:14 are part of a long sentence beginning in 4:11, meaning that each of these verses must be considered in context to the others.²⁶

Verse thirteen speaks of the unity of the body of Christ and that Christians are moving towards the “fullness of Christ” (Ephesians 4:13). As the body of Christ is working to mature, Christ Himself is in turn giving spiritual gifts to aid in that growth.²⁷ Verse fourteen states that part of the maturing process means that Christians are able to access doctrines without mislead. Paul uses the term translated as being tossed “to and fro” which is the same term used in the Book of Luke when the disciples were in a storm on the Sea of Galilee.²⁸ In that situation Christ admonished the disciples for not having enough faith (Luke 8:25). In Ephesians Paul is stating that mature Christians will not be panicked or misled by false doctrines, especially when said doctrine is coming from others intentionally trying to mislead believers “by craftiness in deceitful schemes” (Ephesians 4:14).

²⁴ Sydney Page, “Whose Ministry? a Re-Appraisal of Ephesians 4:12,” *Novum Testamentum* 47, no. 1 (2005): 26-46, 35. JSTOR.

²⁵ E.d. Mbennah, “The Goal of Maturity in Ephesians 4:13-16,” *Acta Theologica* 36, no. 1 (2016): 110. Proquest.

²⁶ Mbennah, 110.

²⁷ Foulkes, 128.

²⁸ Foulkes, 129.

In contrast to the false teachers of verse fourteen, in verse fifteen Paul calls for Christian leaders to “speak the truth in love” (Ephesians 4:15). The word used for speaking, *alētheuontes*, can mean to not only speak but to live out what one is speaking. In this case leaders counter false doctrine by not only speaking the truth to their congregation, but by being an example and living out that truth as well.²⁹

The final verse from the selection, verse sixteen, brings everything together and finishes out the analogy of the church as the body of Christ. Each person and group of Christians is grafted together, joint by joint. The body of Christ grows in the image of Christ and becomes the new temple of Yahweh.³⁰ As stated throughout the selected verses, the attribute that promotes the growth and unity in Christ is the primary attribute of Yahweh, which is love (John 4:7-12).

Significance

As the Church continues into modern times, it requires leaders with spiritual gifts from the Holy Spirit. As stated previously two of the positions listed in verse eleven, apostles and prophets, are no longer part of the Church on Earth.³¹ However, the evangelist, pastor, and teacher are all important current positions. Evangelists are now more commonly called missionaries are continuing to plant new churches in areas of the Earth where the Gospel is still gaining footholds such as some nations in Asia and Africa.

²⁹ Grant R. Osborne, *Ephesians: Verse by Verse* (Bellingham, WA: Lexham Press, 2017), 132. Logos.

³⁰ Nicholas T. Wright, *Paul and the Faithfulness of God* (Fortress Press, 2013), 729. Kindle.

³¹ J. H. Bernard, “Prophets and Prophecy in New Testament Times,” *The Biblical World* 25, no. 2 (1905): 117-124, 123. It appears that apostles and prophets with their concentrations of spiritual gifts to work miracles were no longer needed after the Apostolic period. Perhaps the Church and the New Testament were established enough at that point that these positions were no longer necessary. That is not to say that individuals since then have not been given certain spiritual gifts that were part of the position of apostle or prophet.

Just like in the early period of the Church, missionary evangelists sometimes face imprisonment, harm, and even death as part of their ministry in nations such as India³² and North Korea.³³ Not all missions are as dangerous and there are many youth groups and others that spend time helping new churches form in areas where Christianity is not under persecution.

Pastors and teachers are active as leadership roles in every congregation. Their titles may vary, but the two positions listed in Ephesians are crucial to the spiritual formation and maturity of every congregation. Pastors lead as managers of their congregations and worship leaders. They also act as spiritual counselors and even with Christian counseling services and other mental health professionals, many parishioners prefer to turn to their pastors first in times of crisis.³⁴

Paul's warning about false doctrine in verse fourteen is as important today as it was for the church at Ephesus. In an age of "fake news" and social media,³⁵ the pastor and the teacher have an important role in helping their congregation to understand sound doctrine and exegesis while not being thrown "to-and-fro" by a multitude of heresies from both the misled and opponents of the faith.

³² Steven T. McFarland, "Missionaries and Indigenous Evangelists: The Right to Bear Witness in International Law," *Cumberland Law Review* 31, no. 3 (2001): 599-600.

³³ Anugrah Kumar, "Missionaries Risk Their Lives Returning to North Korea to Spread the Gospel," *Christian Post*, April 7, 2018, accessed May 4, 2019, <https://www.christianpost.com/news/missionaries-risk-their-lives-returning-north-korea-spread-gospel.html>.

³⁴ David G. Benner and Peter C. Hill, "Pastoral Counseling," *Baker Encyclopedia of Psychology and Counseling* (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker., 1999), p. 834.

³⁵ David M. Lazer et al., "The Science of Fake News," *Science* 359, no. 6380 (March 9, 2018): 1094-1096, 1094-1095.

Also, in times of partisanship where spiritual and secular issues draw sharp divides³⁶, pastors and teachers speak and act in truth and love, helping their congregations and the body of Christ at large to be built up in love and unity³⁷.

Conclusion

Paul's writing in Ephesians chapter four pertains to all Christians both now and going forward as he proclaims that Christ now fills the cosmos from the depths of the Earth to the highest heavens and beyond (Ephesians 4:9-10). Here on Earth His followers have spiritual gifts that have been given through the Holy Spirit. Some of these followers have been chosen to be pastors and teachers and their gifts reflect their calling. In the end, Christ has defeated death and freed His followers from being captives in Sheol (Ephesians 4:8). Going forward all Christians can know that He has been given all authority (Ephesians 1:19-21) and believers can find eternal life through him (John 3:16) as part of the body of Christ.

³⁶ "Political Polarization in the American Public," *Pew Research Center for the People and the Press* (Pew Research Center for the People and the Press, October 11, 2016), last modified October 11, 2016, accessed May 5, 2019, <https://www.people-press.org/2014/06/12/political-polarization-in-the-american-public/>.

³⁷ Paul would not believe that the deceitful scheming would only involve people. In chapter six he goes on to warn that Christians struggle against not only humans, but evil spirits that were very real and involved in personal and world events (Ephesians 6:12).

Bibliography

- Benner, David G., and Peter C. Hill. "Pastoral Counseling." *Baker Encyclopedia of Psychology and Counseling*. Grand Rapids, MI: Baker., 1999. Logos.
- Bernard, J. H. "Prophets and Prophecy in New Testament Times." *The Biblical World* 25, no. 2 (1905): 117–124. JSTOR.
- Comfort, Philip Wesley., and Peter H. Davids. *Cornerstone Biblical Commentary: Ephesians, Philippians, Colossians, 1 & 2 Thessalonians, Philemon*. Vol. 15. Carol Stream, IL: Tyndale House Publishers, 2008. Logos.
- Elwell, Walter A., and Barry J. Beitzel. *Baker Encyclopedia of the Bible*. Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Book House, 1988. Logos.
- Foulkes, Francis. *Ephesians: An Introduction and Commentary*. Downers Grove, IL: InterVarsity Press, 2008. Logos.
- Furnish, Victor Paul. *The Anchor Yale Bible Dictionary*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press, 2009. Logos.
- Gray, Patrick. 2012. *Opening Paul's Letters: A Reader's Guide to Genre and Interpretation*. Grand Rapids: Baker Academic. Accessed April 7, 2019. ProQuest Ebook Central.
- Hawthorne, Gerald F., Ralph P. Martin, and Daniel G. Reid. "Paraenesis." *Dictionary of Paul and His Letters: A Compendium of Contemporary Biblical Scholarship*. Erscheinungsort nicht ermittelbar: InterVarsity Press, 2015.
- Heiser, Michael S. *Reversing Hermon: Enoch, the Watchers & the Forgotten Mission of Jesus Christ*. Crane, MO: Defender Publishing, 2017. Kindle.
- Heiser, Michael S. *Unseen Realm*. Lexham Press, 2015. Kindle.
- Kaiser, Walter C., and Silva Moisés. *An Introduction to Biblical Hermeneutics: The Search for Meaning*. Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2007. Wordsearch Bible.
- Kumar, Anugrah. "Missionaries Risk Their Lives Returning to North Korea to Spread the Gospel." *Christian Post*, April 7, 2018. Accessed May 4, 2019. <https://www.christianpost.com/news/missionaries-risk-their-lives-returning-north-korea-spread-gospel.html>.
- Lazer, David M., Matthew A. Baum, Yochai Benkler, and Adam J. Berinsky. "The Science of Fake News." *Science* 359, no. 6380 (March 9, 2018): 1094–1096.

Lea, Thomas D., and David Alan Black. *The New Testament: Its Background and Message*. Nashville, TN: Broadman & Holman Publishers, 2007. Wordsearch Bible.

McFarland, Steven T. "Missionaries and Indigenous Evangelists: The Right to Bear Witness in International Law." *Cumberland Law Review*, vol. 31, no. 3, 2001, pp. 599–600.

Mbennah, E.d. "The Goal of Maturity in Ephesians 4:13-16." *Acta Theologica* 36, no. 1 (2016): 110. Proquest.

Osborne, Grant R. *Ephesians: Verse by Verse*. Bellingham, WA: Lexham Press, 2017. Logos.

Page, Sydney. "Whose Ministry? a Re-Appraisal of Ephesians 4:12." *Novum Testamentum* 47, no. 1 (2005): 26–46. JSTOR.

"Political Polarization in the American Public." *Pew Research Center for the People and the Press*. Pew Research Center for the People and the Press, October 11, 2016. Last modified October 11, 2016. Accessed May 5, 2019. <https://www.people-press.org/2014/06/12/political-polarization-in-the-american-public/>.

Wright, Nicholas T. *Paul and the Faithfulness of God*. Fortress Press, 2013. Kindle.